

Flexcrash

D5.4 Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards

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Executive Summary

The main objective of the standardisation activities is to contribute to the generation of new standards that can facilitate the acceptance and utilisation by the market of the developed solutions and products.

An initial analysis of the standardisation landscape has to be performed, about existing standards that can be related as well as the related standardisation committees and organisations involved.

The availability of this information at the very early stage of the projects will allow using already existing material and the alignment with current and underdevelopment standardisation works facilitating the compatibility of the outcomes with the current market practises.

The Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE), as a European standardisation body, is a partner in the FLEXCRASH project to provide support regarding the standardisation tasks included in the project. In order to fulfil this commitment, this deliverable D5.4 "Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards" has been prepared to guide the partners about the published standards and standards under development that can be applicable to FLEXCRASH.

This deliverable contains the fields of interest related to FLEXCRASH project, given by its consortium, and, from this starting point, an identification and analysis of the standardisation technical committees (TCs) related with the project as well as of the published standards and standards under development that can be useful and relevant for the project activities. Furthermore, it can help in the future to identify standardisation gaps that can be covered by the results of the project.

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Terminology and Acronyms

AFNOR	Association Française de Normalisation (in English: French Standardization Association)
AM	Additive Manufacturing
BSI	British Standards Institution
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC (CLC)	European Committee for Standardization in the Electrical field
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
DIN	Deutsches Institut für Normung (in English: German Institute for Standardization)
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EN	European Standard
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FP	Framework Programme
HEN	Harmonised European Standard
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization; International Standard
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
NSB	National Standardization Body
NWI	New Work Item
PAS	Publicly Available Specification
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
UNE	Asociación Española de Normalización (in English: Spanish Association for Standardisation)
VA	Vienna Agreement
WG	Working Group
WI	Work Item
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The main objective of FLEXCRASH is to develop a flexible and hybrid manufacturing technology based on applying surface patterns by additive manufacturing onto preformed parts to produce tailored adaptive crash-tolerant structures made of green aluminium alloys.

UNE as participant of the WP5 “Dissemination and exploitation” is the leader of Task 5.3. “Standardization activities”, which is related to the present deliverable.

This Deliverable D5.4 "Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards " is the first deliverable for task T5.3 “Standardization activities” inside WP5 “Dissemination and exploitation”.

The purpose of the D5.4 is to provide information on the standardization landscape and applicable standards relevant for FLEXCRASH Project. It pretends to provide starting information for the work packages ensuring compatibility and interoperability with already existing solutions by identifying existing standards and standards under development at European and international levels and facilitate the acceptance and utilization by the market of the developed solutions.

2. Short introduction about standardisation

Standards are voluntary technical documents that set out requirements for a specific item, material, component, system or service, or they describe in detail a particular method, procedure or best practice. Standards are developed and defined through a process of sharing knowledge and building consensus among technical experts nominated by interested parties and other stakeholders - including businesses, consumers and environmental groups, among others. These experts are organised in Technical Committees (TCs), which are subdivided in subcommittees (SCs) or working groups (WGs). These TCs are included in the structure of the standardisation organizations (National, European and International, with the respective mirror committees) and work following their internal regulations.

The standardisation bodies operate at National (UNE, AFNOR, BSI, DIN, etc.), Regional (CEN, CENELEC, ETSI) or International (ISO, IEC, ITU) level. Sometimes there are different standardisation bodies at the same level but covering different fields. This is the case of ISO (general), IEC (electrical) and ITU (telecommunications) at International level, or CEN, CENELEC and ETSI at European level in the same way.

There are also different kinds of standardization documents. The most widespread is the standard, which has a different code depending on the organization under which it was developed, e.g. EN for European Standards, ISO or IEC for International standards. Other types of documents are technical specifications (TS), technical reports (TR) and workshop agreements (CWA). Further amendments to the standards are identified by adding A1, A2, etc. at the end of the standard code.

At European level, all the members of CEN and CENELEC shall adopt EN standards as national standards and have to withdraw any existing national standards which could

conflict with them. A summary of the characteristics of the different standardization documents could be found in the following table.

Table 1. Characteristics of different standardization documents

Type	International code	European code	National code	Main characteristics
Standard	ISO IEC	EN	UNE, NF, BS, DIN, etc. When adopting: UNE-EN, NF-EN, UNE ISO, NF-ISO, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: 3 years • 2 steps of member approval • European: compulsory national adoption • Revision: every 5 years
Technical Specification	ISO/TS IEC/TS	CEN/TS CLC/TS	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TS, NF-CEN/TS, UNE-ISO/TS, NF-ISO/TS, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: 21 months • 1 step of member approval or internal approval in TC • European: optional national adoption • Revision: at 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)
Technical Report	ISO/TR IEC/TR	CEN/TR CLC/TR	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TR, NF-CEN/TR, UNE-ISO/TR, NF-ISO/TR, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal approval in TC • European: optional national adoption • No revision required
Workshop Agreement	IWA	CWA	Variable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: free timeframe (usually few months) • Internal approval in the Workshop • European: optional national adoption • Revision: at 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)

European and International standardization organizations (e.g. CEN and ISO) have signed formal agreements in order to avoid duplication of efforts and promote global relevance of standards, which allow to adopt or develop in parallel each other's standards with the same content and code.

The technical collaboration between ISO and CEN was formalized through the Vienna Agreement (VA).

European standards developed through the Vienna Agreement have EN ISO codification while International Standards developed through the Vienna Agreement remain only with ISO code.

Concerning CENELEC, it has close cooperation with its international counterpart, the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) through the Frankfurt Agreement (FA).

As a result, new electrical standards projects are jointly planned between CENELEC and IEC, and where possible most are carried out at international level. This means that CENELEC will first offer a New Work Item (NWI) to its international counterpart. If

accepted, CENELEC will cease working on the NWI. If IEC refuses, CENELEC will work on the standards content development, keeping IEC closely informed and giving IEC the opportunity to comment at the public enquiry stage. CENELEC and IEC vote in parallel (both organizations are voting at the same time) during the standardization process. If the outcome of the parallel voting is positive, CENELEC will ratify the European standard and the IEC will publish the international standard. Close to 80% of CENELEC standards are identical to or based on IEC publications.

National standards could also be proposed as a base for new European or International standards.

The following figure shows the possible tracks of the standards.

Figure 1. Possible tracks of standards adoption

Therefore, the code of any standard is the combination of the above mentioned issues and could be explained as shown in the following figure.

Figure 2. Example of identification of elements in the code of a standard

3. Methodology

For the identification of standards and standards under development relevant for FLEXCRASH project, the following methodology has been followed:

1. A list of key concepts was prepared to act as a starting point for the identification of standardization areas.
2. For the selection of the key concepts, the aims and goals of the project and the levels in which the project should integrate were taken into account. In addition, the use cases' needs were considered. The list was agreed by UNE and FLEXCRASH partners.

The final list of key concepts used for the search is shown in the following table.

Table 2. List of key concepts acting as a starting point for the identification of standardization areas

Key concepts
Aluminium alloys
Automation processes
Automotive sector
Industrial processes
Mechanical testing
Methods of testing
Manufacturing forming processes
Industrial automation systems in general
Industrial process measurement and control
Road vehicles
Testing of metals
Aluminium structures
Virtual test
Crash test
Laser Metal Deposition (LMD)
Laser Direct Energy Deposition (L-DED)

Reinforcement structure by Additive Manufacturing
Atomization process to produce aluminium powders

- Both standards and standards under development were identified for each standardization area, together with the technical committee responsible for the respective standards.

To facilitate the activity, the key concepts have been grouped into four large areas, namely:

- Materials. It includes information about aluminium alloys and structures.
- Test: It includes information about mechanical, virtual and crash tests as well as methods of testing and testing of metals excluding safety and impact testing of road vehicles that are included in the automotive sector.
- Manufacturing and industrial process. It includes information about industrial and automation processes.
- Automotive sector. It includes information about road vehicles and safety and impact testing.

The search covered the European standardization developed by the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), European Committee for Standardization in the Electrical field CENELEC (CLC), European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) and International standardization developed by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and IEC (electro technical). The databases and websites used for the search are referred in Chapter 6.

As a result of the searching process an Excel file was prepared by UNE including developed standards and standards under development and technical bodies.

- As a final stage, FLEXCRASH partners were asked to identify those references that should really be considered for the project, specifying in what WP they would be used, how the standard would influence/impact the project implementation and risks/opportunities from technical and business perspective.

They were also asked to indicate if any contribution to the respective standard was expected and whether they considered relevant to contact the technical committee responsible for the standard development.

The interaction with the identified standardization technical committee could take place through:

- The participation of one or more FLEXCRASH partners in the technical body (standardization is an open activity and all interested parties may participate in a CEN/CENELEC/ISO/IEC technical committee through the designation of National Standardization Bodies/National Mirror Committee or as organization liaison representative in a CEN/TC).

- The participation through the formal liaison of the FLEXCRASH project with main CEN/TC(s) to participate directly as liaison organization which intend to make technical contributions to their works.
 - The dissemination of the FLEXCRASH project progress by delivering reports to the relevant TCs secretaries or by attending relevant technical committees meetings.
5. As a result of all the process described above a list of technical committees and standards relevant for FLEXCRASH has been identified (see Chapter 4). They have been classified as:
- Relevant technical committees for the project.
 - Relevant standards for the project: it should be decided whether the standards will represent a requirement for the WP developments at design/development phases or it would be interesting to keep them in mind as they could be helpful, but they will not represent a requirement.

4. Relevant standards for FLEXCRASH

4.1 Technical Committees identification

The following table includes a list of the European and international committees, subcommittees and working groups that have been identified as technical bodies working on issues related to the FLEXCRASH project.

Table 3. List of European and international committees related to FLEXCRASH project

Key concept	Technical body	Committee Title
MATERIALS Aluminium alloys Aluminium structures	CEN/TC 132	Aluminium and aluminium alloys
	CEN/TC 135	Execution of steel structures and aluminium structures
	CEN/TC 250/SC 9	Eurocode 9: Design of aluminium structures
	ISO/TC 226	Materials for the production of primary aluminium
	ISO/TC 167	Steel and aluminium structures
	ISO/TC 79	Light metals and their alloys
TEST Mechanical testing Methods of testing Testing of metals Virtual test Crash test	CEN/TC 138	Non-destructive testing
	CEN/TC 262	Metallic and other inorganic coatings, including for corrosion protection and corrosion testing of metals and alloys
	CEN/TC 459/SC 1	Test methods for steel (other than chemical analysis)
	CEN/TC 226	Road equipment
	CEN/WS FORMPLANET	Innovative testing in support of the sheet metal forming industry

	ISO/TC 135	Non-destructive testing
	ISO/TC 156	Corrosion of metals and alloys
	ISO/TC 164	Mechanical testing of metals
MANUFACTURING AND INDUSTRIAL PROCESS Automation processes Industrial processes Manufacturing forming processes Industrial automation systems in general Industrial process measurement and control Laser Metal Deposition (LMD) Laser Direct Energy Deposition (L-DED) Atomization process to produce aluminium powders Reinforcement structure by Additive Manufacturing	CEN/TC 310	Advanced automation technologies and their applications
	CEN/TC 121	Welding and allied processes
	CLC/TC 65X	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation
	CEN/TC 438	Additive Manufacturing
	CEN/CLC/WS ZDMTerm	Zero Defects in Digital Manufacturing Terminology
	CEN/CLC/WS EFPFInterOp	European Connected Factory Platform for Agile Manufacturing Interoperability
	CEN/WS FORMPLANET	Innovative testing in support of the sheet metal forming industry
	ISO/TC 184	Automation systems and integration
	ISO/TC 119	Powder metallurgy
	ISO/TC 261	Additive manufacturing
AUTOMOTIVE SECTOR Automotive sector Road vehicles	CEN/TC 301	Road vehicles
	CEN/WS 113	Framework linking dismantled parts with new design components for the automotive industry in a circular economy model
	ISO/TC 22	Road vehicles
	ISO/TC 22/SC 36	"Safety and impact testing"

4.2 Relevant standards

Thanks to the feedback received from partners, additional standards potentially related to the project were included. Further standards not comprised in the previous list were identified by partners and so added to the revised catalogue.

In order to present the list in a coherent and understandable way, the list of relevant standards has been grouped by the responsible Technical Committee.

CEN/TC 121 - Welding and allied processes

Scope: Standardization of welding by all processes, as well as allied processes; these standards include terminology, definitions and the symbolic representation of welds on drawings, apparatus and equipment for welding, raw materials (gas, parent and filler metals) welding processes and rules, methods of inspection, testing and quality control, design of welded joints, qualification of welding personnel, as well as safety and health.

Excluded: Electrical arc welding equipment and electrical safety matters related to welding which are the responsibility of CLC/TC 26; welding and brazing for aerospace application which is the responsibility of ASD-STAN/D4/WG4.

Table 4. CEN/TC 121 relevant standards for Flexcrash

Standard code	Standard Title	Date of publication	Related WP	Comments
EN ISO 13919-2:2021	Electron and laser-beam welded joints - Requirements and recommendations on quality levels for imperfections - Part 2: Aluminium, magnesium and their alloys and pure copper (ISO 13919-2:2021)	2021-08-31	WP2	Not directly related for different material, but may be useful
EN ISO 13919-1:2019	Electron and laser-beam welded joints - Requirements and recommendations on quality levels for imperfections - Part 1: Steel, nickel, titanium and their alloys (ISO 13919-1:2019)	2020-05-31	WP2	
EN 1011-6:2018	This document gives general guidance for laser beam welding and associated processes of metallic materials in all forms of product (e.g. cast, wrought, extruded, forged). NOTE Some guidance on laser beam cutting, drilling, surface treatment and cladding is given in Annex F.	2019-06-30	WP2	
EN ISO 15609-4:2009	Specification and qualification of welding procedures for metallic materials - Welding procedure specification - Part 4: Laser beam welding (ISO 15609-4:2009)	2009-11-30	WP2	
EN ISO 15614-11:2002	Specification and qualification of welding procedures for metallic materials - Welding procedure test - Part 11: Electron and laser beam welding (ISO 15614-11:2002)	2002-09-30	WP2	
prEN ISO 15614-11	Specification and qualification of welding procedures for metallic materials - Welding procedure test - Part 11: Electron and laser beam welding (ISO/DIS 15614-11:2022)	2024-09-02*	WP2	

*In the standards under development the estimated date of publication is included

CEN/TC 438 - Additive Manufacturing

Scope: Standardization in the field of Additive Manufacturing (AM)

Table 5. CEN/TC 438 relevant standards for Flexcrash

Standard code	Standard Title	Date of publication	Related WP	Comments
CEN ISO/ASTM/TR 52906:2022	Additive manufacturing - Non-destructive testing - Intentionally seeding flaws in metallic parts (ISO/ASTM/TR 52906:2022)	2022-05-18	WP2	Identification of the best non-destructive testing for both development phase and future production
EN ISO/ASTM 52950:2021	Additive manufacturing - General principles - Overview of data processing (ISO/ASTM 52950:2021)	2021-08-31	WP2	
EN ISO/ASTM 52907:2019	Additive manufacturing - Feedstock materials - Methods to characterize metal powders (ISO/ASTM 52907:2019)	2020-06-30	WP2	

EN ISO/ASTM 52910:2019	Additive manufacturing - Design - Requirements, guidelines and recommendations (ISO/ASTM 52910:2018)	2020-04-30	WP1/WP2	
EN ISO 17296-3:2016	Additive manufacturing - General principles - Part 3: Main characteristics and corresponding test methods (ISO 17296-3:2014)	2017-03-31	WP2	
prCEN ISO/ASTM TR 52905	Additive manufacturing of metals - Non-destructive testing and evaluation - Defect detection in parts (ISO/ASTM DTR 52905:2023)	2023-07-31*	WP2	
prEN ISO/ASTM 52926-4	Additive Manufacturing of metals - Qualification principles - Part 4: Qualification of operators for DED-LB (ISO/ASTM DIS 52926-4:2022)	2024-03-06*	WP2	
prEN ISO/ASTM 52926-5	Additive Manufacturing of metals - Qualification principles - Part 5: Qualification of operators for DED-Arc (ISO/ASTM DIS 52926-5:2022)	2024-03-06*	WP2	
prEN ISO/ASTM 52929	Additive manufacturing of metals – Powder bed fusion – Presentation of material properties in material data sheets	2025-10-14*	WP2	
prEN ISO/ASTM 52953	Additive Manufacturing for metals -- General Principles -- Registration of geometric data acquired from process-monitoring and for quality control	2025-09-24*	WP2	

** In the standards under development the estimated date of publication is included*

5. Conclusions

As a result of the study of the standardisation landscape through the methodology explained above, several standards relevant for the FLEXCRASH project have been found. They are specially linked to WP2 referring to manufacturing processes such as welding and allied processes and additive manufacturing.

This initial analysis of the standardization landscape is useful at the very early stage of the project because it reveals already existing material and promotes the alignment with current and under development standardization work, facilitating the compatibility of the outcomes with the current market practises. Project partners collaboration and their feedback have been very important and useful for this analysis.

Despite not having found only a specific standardization technical committee whose activity impacts directly on the FLEXCRASH project, specific tasks to be addressed in the project are related to standardization works, and several technical committees have been identified as possibly most relevant

On the other hand, the identified standards might be considered as a compliance requirement for the outputs of the project or they could be used as guidelines since they could be useful for the WPs.

After this analysis of the current standardization situation of the technical committees and standards related to FLEXCRASH, one main conclusion may be drawn:

There is a large number of European and international technical committees, as well as of standards and standards under development related to FLEXCRASH project that may be useful for its development and for its future dissemination. Depending on the

assessment by FLEXCRASH partners on the impact of the identified standardization committees on their tasks and the level of contribution that their results can represent for these committees, several actions can be performed, like:

- the follow up of the standardization activity through updates reported by UNE;
- the follow up through one or more FLEXCRASH representatives joining this standardization committees. Standardization is an open activity and all interested parties may participate in a CEN/CENELEC/ISO/IEC technical committee through its National Mirror Committee and National Standardization Body;
- the dissemination of the FLEXCRASH project progress by delivering reports to the relevant TCs secretaries or by attending relevant technical committees' meetings.

To use the standardisation system as a tool for dissemination of the project results, an interaction with the market stakeholders will be necessary to decide the type of FLEXCRASH's engagement with relevant standardization technical committees. UNE will provide the necessary technical support required for that interaction.

It is also important to mention that as the project progresses, new standards or technical committees may be detected as relevant. In these cases, the same methodology will be followed.

6. References

For the elaboration of this report, the following sources have been consulted:

- CEN Website (www.cen.eu)
- CENELEC Website (www.cenelec.eu)
- CEN/CENELEC Projex Online database (projex.cen.eu) (restricted to authorized users)
- ETSI Website (www.etsi.org)
- ISO Website (www.iso.org)
- ISO Project Portal (isotc.iso.org) (restricted to authorized users)
- IEC Website (www.iec.ch)